

CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

Linking Research & Innovation for
Gender Equality

D5.5 CALIPER Charter

WP5 - Engagement, change
management and sustainability

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© CALIPER Consortium, 2020

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Document information

Grant Agreement Number	873134	Acronym	CALIPER	
Full Title	The CALIPER project: Linking research and innovation for gender equality			
Topic	SwafS-09-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans			
Funding scheme	CSA – Coordination and Support Action			
Start Date	1 st January 2020	Duration	48 months	
Project URL	http://caliper-project.eu/			
EU Project Officer	Katharina Buse, REA, Unit B5			
Project Coordinator	Vasiliki Moumtzi – VIL Kyriaki Karydou - VIL			
Deliverable	D5.5 CALIPER Charter			
Work Package	WP5 – Engagement, Change Management and Sustainability			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M48	Actual	M48
Nature	R – Report	Dissemination Level	P - Public	
Lead Beneficiary	Smart Venice			
Responsible Author (s)	Maria Sangiuliano, Marzia Cescon (Smart Venice)			
Reviewer(s):	Kyriaki Karydou (VIL)			
Keywords	Inclusive gender equality, intersectionality, R&I ecosystems, multistakeholder collaboration.			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
0.1	18/12/2023	Draft	1 st level control: Deliverable provided to partners assigned for review	VIL
1	21/12/2023	Final		SV

Executive Summary

The present deliverable contains the CALIPER Charter, that is a final initiative developed by the project with the purpose of creating a durable change in organisations and ecosystems by strengthening the links between scientific research, economy, and society as well as the intersectional and intersectoral approach to gender equality. It aspires to emphasise how internal institutional change can be fostered through the involvement of external stakeholders in structural change.

The principal target of the deliverable is a diverse group of stakeholders, that includes research organisations, public research bodies, private research enterprises and policy makers in the field of R&I.

Table of contents

Executive Summary.....	4
Table of contents	5
1 Introduction. The CALIPER Charter: why, for whom and the endorsement process	6
2 The CALIPER Charter: values, principles, and commitments to action	8
2.1 Driving inclusive gender equality in research and innovation: linking institutional and ecosystems change	8
2.2 Redefining innovation: bridging social and tech realms, towards inclusiveness.....	9
2.3 Inclusive, safe, and gender-based violence-free work and study environments in R&I ecosystems	11
3 The CHARTER step by step guidelines	13
3.1 How to sign/endorse the Charter	13
3.2 Disseminating and promoting the CALIPER Charter	14
3.3 Implementing the charter commitments via collaborative efforts in your R&I ecosystem	16
4 Annexes.....	18
4.1 Brief facts on gender and other inequalities in R&I	19
4.2 EU policies to tackle gender and other gaps crossing research and innovation domains	20
4.3 In progress list of signatories	21

1 Introduction. The CALIPER Charter: why, for whom and the endorsement process

In an era where research and innovation play a pivotal role in shaping societies and economies, it has never been more important to foster inclusiveness and gender equality within these sectors. The CALIPER Charter represents a response by the CALIPER consortium partners, within an evolving European landscape of policies on inclusive gender equality in research and innovation (see Annex, [Chapter 4.2](#)). Building on the European Union's active promotion of gender equality in research since 2012, the CALIPER Charter represents a transformative initiative designed to create lasting change in organisations and innovation ecosystems.

The Horizon 2020 CALIPER project has adopted an innovative approach to setting up/implementing Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in its participating RPOs/RFOs¹, aligning with the 2020 European Research Area (ERA) “inclusive” GEP dimensions, which foster intersectional, intersectoral and geographic inclusiveness.

In line with the [2020 Communication on the new European Research Area \(ERA\)](#) and [ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024](#), gender equality policies in R&I have progressed towards a more complex framework that looks at gender in conjunction with other potential discrimination grounds (intersectional inclusiveness), expands from public research and HEI institutions to the innovation and private sectors (intersectoral inclusiveness), and seeks interventions that are context-sensitive (geographical inclusiveness). This transformative agenda is underpinned by the Charter and seeks to strengthen the links between scientific research, the economy and society.

The CALIPER Charter embraces these principles and emphasises how internal institutional change through inclusive Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) can be enhanced by forming partnerships and leveraging synergies with external stakeholders, allowing for an impact that extends beyond organisational boundaries. This approach has been tested for the entire CALIPER project cycle. Therefore, the Charter builds upon:

- The CALIPER study on inclusive gender lenses through which to rethink R&I innovation concepts and practices, and exploring the potential of synergies with external stakeholders in GEPs’ design and implementation, conducted within the project and with input from many sister projects and other stakeholders ([Sangiuliano, Cescon & Nason, 2021](#)) and a ‘lessons learned’ paper from the project ([Sangiuliano, Karydou & Kyrkou, 2023](#); Karydou, Sangiuliano, Moumtzi, Kyrkou & Cescon, 2023, at pag. 22 [here](#)).
- The CALIPER design of indicators for the inclusive gender analysis of R&I ecosystems, conducted jointly with the internal assessment of GEPs by implementing institutions ([Sangiuliano & Cescon, 2021](#)).
- The experience of all CALIPER implementing partners in setting up co-creative environments for their GEPs’ design, and creating R&I Hubs ([Aguirre & Manneback, 2021](#)) to promote collaborative actions and measures.

The Charter also promotes the adoption of efforts by which to address gender disparities, empower underrepresented groups, and integrate an intersectional perspective ([Lombardo, Meier, Verloo, 2017](#)), what we refer to as an inclusive gender equality approach. While keeping gender inequalities as its main focus, the Charter promotes diversity, equity and inclusiveness in research and innovation organisations

¹ Research Performing Organisations/Research Funding Organisations

and ecosystems at large. The outlook is on seeking to break down barriers, challenge biases, and ensure that opportunities within the R&I sector are accessible to all, regardless of gender, ethnicity, socio-economic background, or other intersecting factors. Acknowledging that this is a challenging endeavour and that a solid body of knowledge and practical tools are still missing, the Charter is calling for steps in this direction.

The CALIPER Charter seeks to engage a diverse group of stakeholders as potential and desired signatories. It is designed to target research organisations, educational institutions, public research bodies, private research-intensive enterprises, and policymakers in the field of R&I, to stand up and express their endorsement of the Charter's principles and commitments. Civil society organisations are also considered important players in R&I ecosystems and are thus invited to endorse the Charter. Even if some of the commitments/principles might not seem as fully relevant to some of them, we believe their role and voices are key to be taken on board in the journey towards more gender equal and inclusive R&I ecosystems. The CALIPER Charter is open to both individual and organisational/institutional endorsement, as can be specified in the specific forms, available on the dedicated [CALIPER Charter Web pages](#). Signature and endorsement are not meant to be legally binding, as further explained in Paragraph 3.1.

The document's structure includes:

1. A main chapter ([Chapter 2](#)) that is the core of the Charter, with its three key blocks of principles and values, and the respective commitments to action;
2. A step-by-step guideline chapter ([Chapter 3](#)) on how to endorse, disseminate and implement the Charter;
3. Two brief chapters as Annexes ([Chapter 4](#)) on the key facts and figures ([Chapter 4.1](#)) and the EU policies ([Chapter 4.2](#)) that motivate the need for and the rationale of such a document.

2 The CALIPER Charter: values, principles, and commitments to action

As signatories to the CALIPER Charter, which includes both individuals and organisations, we state publicly that we adhere to the values and principles that are included in the following paragraphs. Consistent with those principles and reflected in the Charter's sections on Commitment to Action, we will make our best possible efforts in pledging to apply these as concrete actions within our working practice and/or volunteering/activism initiatives. We commit to act as inward and outward change agents, promoting transformation toward gender equality and inclusiveness, both in our own institutions/organisations and within our nations/regions and innovation ecosystems. To the best of our possibilities within our roles and positions, we will strive to make the principles and values of the CALIPER Charter come to reality in the geographic, socio-economic, organisational contexts and cultures in which we operate, with the necessary adaptations if relevant. We might be able to implement commitments gradually and/or partially but will make sure that those are advocated for in our own environment, on a long-term basis.

2.1 Driving inclusive gender equality in research and innovation: linking institutional and ecosystems change

Starting and prioritising institutional/organisational change is key to achieving gender equality in scientific research and innovation, and Gender Equality Plans are crucial tools to accomplish this. Also, particularly in organisations and countries where these policies have gained more support over the years, integration with DEI (Diversity, Equality, and Inclusion) strategies and the adoption of an inclusive and intersectional gender approach are the way forward. However, individual efforts from academic and non-academic actors within R&I cannot suffice if we want to accelerate the pace of change. In this respect, we, the signatories, acknowledge the principles highlighted in the following paragraph.

2.1.1 Principles and values

The complexity of interconnections and interdependencies at the level of R&I ecosystems needs to be acknowledged when planning for change. This complexity includes education (from early stages to higher education, and vocational education and training) public and private research, industrial and societal uptake of innovations, and the results of scientific research, as well as the employment they generate. All these elements are closely interlinked, and similar inequality challenges are shared by different organisations in the same countries/regions. This calls for orchestrated solutions, as gaps generated in one link in the chain will propagate in the next ones.

Virtuous cycles can be triggered and should be pursued between fostering inward change (at the level of organisations) and outward change within respective R&I ecosystems at the territorial (city, regional, national) levels. To facilitate this, leveraging existing networks, consortia, partnerships, and creating ad-hoc ones where appropriate can be useful.

Intersectoral collaboration and synergies within R&I ecosystems are pivotal. These can take the form of dedicated inclusive gender equality measures and/or a focus on mainstreaming and integrating an inclusive gender perspective within existing actions, programs and projects.

2.1.2 Commitment to action

We will:

- Promote, advocate and sustain the adoption of Inclusive Gender Equality Plans and Diversity and Inclusion Plans in our own organisation, and include actions/measures that are designed and implemented in collaboration with external actors from within the R&I ecosystems, where located.
- Undertake inclusive gender-sensitive mapping and assessment of existing networks, collaborations, and partnerships within the relevant R&I ecosystem, so as to identify areas for improvement and collaboration.
- Design and use measurable indicators that are sensitive to gender and other intersected inequalities for mapping, monitoring and assessing initiatives at the level of our own organisation, as well as at R&I ecosystem level in cases of multistakeholder collaborative actions and initiatives.
- Share disaggregated data along gender and other intersected discrimination grounds with stakeholders we collaborate with, and join forces in data collection tools, whenever possible.
- Strengthen collaborative efforts and actions among different stakeholder types, within GEPs and parallel to GEPs, aimed at addressing gender and other intersected inequalities that impact our different institutions and spread positive effects to our respective networks.

2.2 Redefining innovation: bridging social and tech realms, towards inclusiveness

We, as signatories of the CALIPER Charter, embrace a critical view of innovation challenges, established norms and mainstream interpretations while addressing power imbalances. Innovation practices are evolving from closed, linear, and tech-driven approaches to more open, interdisciplinary, and culture-based models. This shift prioritises systemic, co-created innovation. It values not only technology transfer projects and industry-funded research, but also emphasises science communication and citizen science as crucial areas for academic and research organisations to invest in for strategic positioning. As signatories, we believe in the principles and values described in the paragraph below.

2.2.1 Principles and values

- Changes and new paradigms in innovation processes need to be steered and monitored to make sure that they do not reproduce or exacerbate existing gender and intersected inequalities. On the contrary, it is important to mainstream an inclusive gender perspective in open innovation and co-creative dynamics so as to promote inclusiveness and equity of R&I processes and ecosystems.
- There is indeed an “innovation case” for inclusive gender equality in the sense that this can be a lever for increasing the excellence and quality of innovation, but there is also a need for going deeper and critically deconstructing and rethinking innovation narratives, norms and practices.
- Gender studies have shed light on the inherent bias in traditional definitions of innovation, which tend to revolve around male-centric subjects and values. This bias has persisted, due to the historical association of innovation mostly with technology, infrastructure and tangible products, leaving aside innovation in social/welfare/service-related domains. Given the persistent gender segregation in STEM disciplines, it is not surprising that the perception of innovation and innovators often carries masculine traits.

- To address this issue, we advocate for a broader understanding of innovation, considering the social economy, welfare, and creative industries as essential drivers of innovation. In fact, these sectors tend to have a higher representation of employed women, and the ways they operate are being radically transformed by digital technologies as well, not always taking into account and valuing their needs and perspectives.
- Furthermore, the prevailing definitions of innovation often carry an implicit bias towards exceptional, ground-breaking innovations. However, it's essential to recognise that innovation can also emerge gradually from everyday practices. It does not always require inventing something entirely new, it is not limited to technology alone; it often stems from everyday activities and adaptations, while tech and social innovations can leverage each other. To foster a more diverse and equitable innovation landscape, multiple voices, needs and perspectives must be heard and engaged in co-creating solutions: civil society representatives, actors from the social economy sectors, representatives from women and minorities can be considered as ecosystem stakeholders.

2.2.2 Commitment to action

We will:

- Actively work to ensure that innovation processes do not perpetuate gender and other intersected inequalities, and actively promote inclusive gender perspectives in open innovation, participatory and co-creative dynamics.
- Encourage critical examination of innovation narratives and practices, particularly within one's research, project design and/or institutional or science communication work.
- Support research and initiatives that challenge traditional definitions of innovation, to be more inclusive and reflective of diverse perspectives and values, and that embrace a more comprehensive understanding of innovation that extends beyond technology and tangible products to encompass the social economy, welfare, and creative industries.
- Integrate an intersectionally inclusive gender dimension into scientific research content and methods, when relevant, as well as into product and service design, using good practices and tools such as those devised within transnational projects such as Gendered Innovations.
- Encourage collaboration and synergy between social and tech innovations, recognising that they can complement each other and lead to more diverse and equitable innovation outcomes.
- Adopt a STE(A)M approach when sparking the interest of younger generations in Science and Technology, to highlight creative and interdisciplinary interconnections between STEM, the Arts and Social Science and Humanities
- Invite and engage R&I ecosystems' organisations, networks and individuals that represent civil society, women and minority groups, whenever relevant. When doing so, take into account existing power imbalances that might affect participation (less availability in terms of time and resources) and take adequate measures to ensure support.
- Value gender and intersectionality expertise and knowledge, and promote its exchange and transfer into projects and initiatives (including via training and capacity building).

2.3 Inclusive, safe, and gender-based violence-free work and study environments in R&I ecosystems

Research and innovation sectors offer knowledge intensive employment opportunities that should be open to all, overcoming existing and persistent inequalities. The CALIPER Charter signatories agree in identifying phenomena such as the under-representation of women in R&I as even more seriously affecting the sector as far as leadership positions are concerned. By endorsing the Charter, we the signatories, share the same understanding on the values and principles spotlighted in the following paragraph.

2.3.1 Principles and values

- More girls/women from different backgrounds, as well as people from minority groups, are to be employed in R&I. Diverse mindsets and experiences are needed in research-oriented, managerial, and entrepreneurial positions.
- The impact of gender bias, care-related burdens, and other socio-economic inequalities on working life should be acknowledged and considered in recruitment and human resources management practices and processes.
- Careers in R&I should not require individuals to sacrifice their personal lives in organisational cultures that put at risk the psychological and physical wellbeing of workers.
- Open and flexible study and career paths in and out of academia should be devised, facilitating voluntary transition and career progression from one to the other sectors and vice versa, preserving rights to adequate and just compensation and treatment across sectors.
- R&I organisations and ecosystems can be affected, like any other organisations and networks, by sexist, racist, classist, ableist, homo-transphobic behaviours that need to be prevented, countered, and banned at all levels so as to ensure safe working environments for all.
- When it comes to gender discrimination, gender-based violence is a global crosscutting, and cross-sectoral issue that affects societies in general as well as working places and professional collaborations. It encompasses violence, targeting women from all walks of life and different backgrounds, with potential reinforcing effects in cases of multiple intersected inequalities. It also refers to violence exerted that is based on gender identity against LGBTQI+ persons. From “jokes” to harassment and rape, the problem is deeply rooted in structural inequalities, power relations and cultures at all levels of societies. Thus, partnership and collaboration between different stakeholders can be useful to tackling it so that multiplying effects could be achieved.

2.3.2 Commitment to action

Reflecting the above-mentioned principles and values, we, the signatories of the CALIPER Charter, commit to:

Promote diversity and inclusion in R&I employment

- Use gender-sensitive indicators to collect data on students' enrolment, research and administrative sector employment, patenting, transfer to market and society, and entrepreneurship so as to monitor and detect gender gaps and other inequalities.
- Implement inclusive hiring practices to ensure that more girls, women and individuals from minority groups are employed in research-oriented, managerial and entrepreneurial positions.
- Encourage diverse mindsets and experiences within our organisations and ecosystems.

- Regularly review recruitment processes to eliminate any biases that may exist.

Support open and flexible career paths

- Create open and flexible study and career paths, both within and outside academia, to facilitate voluntary transitions and career progression, while preserving the rights to adequate compensation and fair treatment.
- Provide mentoring and guidance for individuals considering transitions between academia and industry.
- Ensure that individuals can move between sectors without facing discrimination or loss of benefits.

Address gender bias and socio-economic inequalities

We commit to acknowledging and addressing the impact of gender bias, care-related burdens, and other socio-economic inequalities on working life by:

- Developing inclusive human resources management practices that consider these factors during recruitment and career development.
- Implementing policies to support work-life balance and mental health in the workplace.

Ensure safe and inclusive working and collaboration environments

We pledge to create safe and inclusive working, collaboration and partnership environments, both in R&I organisations and ecosystems, by:

- Taking measures to prevent and contrast sexist, racist, classist, ableist, and homo-transphobic behaviours.
- Implementing training and awareness programmes to prevent and address discrimination and harassment.
- Establishing mechanisms for reporting and addressing incidents of discrimination or harassment.
- Partnering with other stakeholders, including organisations within the R&I ecosystem, to tackle gender-based violence.
- Raising awareness and providing education on gender-based violence prevention.
- Creating a culture that prevents and contrasts all forms of gender-based violence, from "jokes" to harassment and assault.

Intersectional approach

We acknowledge that gender inequalities intersect with other forms of inequality. Our commitment includes:

- Recognising and addressing the reinforcing effects of multiple intersected inequalities.
- Ensuring that our efforts to combat inequalities are inclusive and intersectional, taking into account how economic power/hierarchies and socio-economic disadvantage play a role, and the needs and experiences of racialised minorities, LGBTQI+ communities, people with disabilities, etc.

3 The CHARTER step by step guidelines

3.1 How to sign/endorse the Charter

The signature/endorsement process is simple and lean. It is enough to fill in your details on [the dedicated online form](#), made available on the [Charter's pages on the CALIPER project website](#). When considering signing, please take the following into account: even if the aim of the Charter is to multiply and disseminate as well as to stimulate concrete action to implement the values and principles enshrined in the document, **the signature process is not a legally binding type of commitment**. Also, even if endorsement signals that values and principles expressed in the Charter are shared, the commitments exemplify directions for action that might differ depending on organisation type, context, existing policies in place (both internal and external), and many other factors, so the Charter does not intend to be a one-fits-all set of solutions.

Nevertheless, we call on individuals and organisations to perform a thorough ethical consideration of their commitment and not sign only for visibility purposes but only if, to the best of their knowledge, they see the Charter as already aligned with existing or planned efforts to act toward inclusive gender equality in R&I.

As anticipated, both endorsement from individuals and institutional endorsement are welcome, and the difference will be specified in the signature form and made visible on the published list of signatories on the CALIPER website.

Institutional endorsement will be possible in two ways:

- Automatically for individuals who are in a leadership position within their organisation.
- For all the others, by declaring that the leaders/senior managers of the organisations have authorised institutional endorsement.

The infographics in the two chapters below illustrate the suggested path to follow after signing/endorsing the Charter².

It is possible to endorse the Charter till the end of January 2024.

3.2 Disseminating and promoting the CALIPER Charter

In order to increase the awareness of the CALIPER Charter among relevant stakeholders and the general public, five key points have been identified. By following these brief guidelines, synthesized in the infographic below, individuals and organizations can contribute to the effective dissemination and promotion of the CALIPER Charter, fostering a broader understanding and adoption of its principles.

1) Spread the Word

How to do it?

- Utilize institutional social media platforms, newsletters, and other communication channels to share information about the CALIPER charter.
- Encourage your team members to share updates and key achievements related to the Charter on their personal and professional networks.
- Collaborate with partners, influencers, and organizations to amplify the reach of the Charter messages.

2) Be an Ambassador

How to do it?

- Communicate to your networks that you endorse the Charter's principles and signed it.
- Advocate for the CALIPER Charter in different settings such as events, conferences, etc.

3) Tell your Story

How to do it?

- Share your good practices on collaboration on gender equality in R&I.
- Communicate about success stories in your organization related to the implementation of the Charter commitments.
- Fill the form <https://forms.gle/2HY1CpCZDhMVEuB69>.

4) Boost engagement

How to do it?

- Organize events, webinars, workshops with your stakeholders to present the Charter.
- Establish online forums, discussion groups or social media spaces with your community to foster participation and interaction on the Charter's principles.
- Encourage feedback and suggestions from the community on how to implement the Charter.

5) Translate it

How to do it?

- Increase the accessibility of the Charter by translating it in your local language
- Distribute translated versions through various channels to reach a wider and more diverse audience

How to promote the CALIPER Charter

01 SPREAD THE WORD!
On your website, social media platforms, media outlets and newsletters

02 BE AN AMBASSADOR!
Communicate that you have signed the Charter to gather more signatories

03 TELL YOUR STORY
Share your good practise of collaboration on Gender equality in Research & Innovation and get visibility on our communication channels

04 BOOST ENGAGEMENT
Partner with stakeholders to organise online or offline events to present the Charter

05 TRANSLATE
Translating the Charter in national languages could facilitate dissemination even more!

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.

3.3 Implementing the charter commitments via collaborative efforts in your R&I ecosystem

Some guidelines have been also produced for supporting signatories to implement the CALIPER Charter. By following these guidelines, collaborative efforts can effectively drive the realization of the Charter's commitments, fostering change both within organizations and throughout the broader ecosystems.

Five main steps have been identified and are also synthesized in the infographic below:

1) Start from Existing Networks

How to do it?

- Leverage on existing relationships and networks by mapping the R&I ecosystem using inclusive gender lenses.
- Communicate the Charter's vision and seek commitment from existing connections to initiate a foundation for collaboration.
- Explore opportunities to integrate activities related to the Charter's principles into ongoing projects or actions.

2) Choose Allies

How to do it?

- Identify potential allies who have a demonstrated commitment to similar values and share similar challenges.
- Establish clear communication channels to discuss shared objectives and potential collaboration opportunities.
- Foster strong, mutually beneficial relationships with allies through regular communication and collaboration on Charter's commitments.

3) Use Co-Creative Approaches

How to do it?

- Organize workshops and brainstorming sessions using innovative techniques, including design thinking and co-creative approaches.
- Encourage active participation from stakeholders in the co-creation of collaborative actions.
- Implement iterative processes that allow for continuous improvement of collaborations.

4) Double focus

How to do it?

- Ensure that the implementation efforts address both internal organizational changes and broader ecosystem improvements.
- Collaborate with external stakeholders to influence systemic changes and address larger issues within the ecosystem without reducing the efforts towards internal change.
- Balance short-term internal improvements with long-term, sustainable contributions to the broader ecosystem.

5) Make it Sustainable

How to do it?

- Establish practices and structures that ensure the longevity and ongoing impact of collaborative initiatives.
- Make sure actions are sustainable in the long term regarding human and financial resources.
- Integrate Charter’s commitments into organizational values, policies, and long-term strategic plans.

4 References

[Aguirre, S. Manneback, G. D2.2 Reporting results of multistakeholder dialogues, Zenodo, 2021](#)

[BMC Proceedings, Abstracts from the International Conference Diversity Interventions, 2023](#)

[European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Research Area Policy Agenda. Overview of Actions for the Period 2022-2023, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021](#)

[European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Towards inclusive gender equality in research and innovation, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022](#)

[Lombardo, E. Meier, P. Verloo, M. policymaking from Gender+ Equality Perspective, Taylor&Francis online, 2016](#)

[Sangiuliano, M. Cescon, M. D1.1 Internal and external assessment methodologies and guidelines, Zenodo, 2021](#)

[Sangiuliano, M. Cescon, M. Nason, N. D1.3 Gender Analysis of research and innovation ecosystems and reports from the local R&I Hubs, Zenodo, 2021](#)

[Sangiuliano, M. Karydou, K. Kykou, D. It's all about priorities: tips for successfully implementing gender actions, Zenodo, 2023](#)

5 Annexes

5.1 Brief facts on gender and other inequalities in R&I

In 2021, the European Union (EU) saw a notable increase in the number of female scientists and engineers, totalling 6.9 million, which was 369,800 more than in the previous year. Despite this growth, women still represented only 41% of the overall workforce in the science and engineering sectors within the EU. An analysis of various economic sectors revealed varying levels of gender balance. The services sector exhibited a relatively better gender balance, with 46% of scientists and engineers being female. In contrast, other sectors like air transport (28%), manufacturing (21%), science and engineering (21%), motor vehicles (13%), transport equipment (12%), and water transport (8%) showed significantly lower rates of female representation ([Eurostat, 2021](#)). However, gender disparities extended beyond employment statistics. In terms of research funding, men in the EU27 have a higher success rate than women, as they were found to have on average 3.9% more chances than women of accessing research funding in 2019 ([She Figures, 2021](#)). This discrepancy in securing research funding is closely tied to researchers' scientific productivity, as funding agencies heavily consider publication records when making decisions. Nevertheless, from 2015 to 2019, only four out of every ten corresponding authors were women, highlighting the urgent need to incorporate a gender equality perspective into research funding programmes, grants, fellowships, research excellence assessments, peer-review processes, and professional development initiatives ([European Commission, 2021](#)). This calls for collaborative efforts involving academia, research funding bodies, national policymakers in research and innovation, and journal publishers. Additionally, gender disparities are evident in patenting, with a notable gender gap, albeit with some signs of improvement. In 2017, over 25% of PCT (Patent Cooperation Treaty) applications listed at least one woman inventor, according to data from the European Patent Office ([EPO, 2022](#)). Universities, as they increasingly engage in transferring research results to the market and society, face the risk of male domination in activities such as launching university-led or promoted spin-out companies. However, the shortage of comprehensive data on intersectionality, particularly in the context of gender disparities in STEM and migration, remains a challenge. The existing gender and race/ethnicity gaps in STEMM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, and Medicine) sectors have been well-documented, and persist even though there is a gradual increase in the representation of highly qualified female migrants in shortage occupations within these fields ([Bolzani, Crivellaro & Grimaldi, 2021](#); [Cerna & Czaika, 2016](#); [Ouali, 2007](#)).

To address this data gap, the European Commission's She Figures report ([European Commission, 2021](#)) has taken some steps towards acknowledging the issue. The latest version of the report has introduced a glossary that defines terminology related to intersectionality. It also presents the results of an exploratory analysis of Horizon 2020 funded projects integrating intersectional aspects. Out of the 30,084 projects analysed, only 58 included intersectional aspects, indicating that there is much room for improvement in considering intersectionality within scientific research.

The scarcity of intersectional disaggregated data underscores the importance of further research and data collection efforts to understand and address better the unique challenges faced by underrepresented groups in STEMM fields, including among others, LGBTQI+ populations and racialised minorities. A recent publication of the EC has taken stock of the current and emerging actions that address characteristics other than gender in R&I and through inclusive GEPs and are in the early stages of development, underlining recommendations towards concrete implementation ([European Commission, 2022](#)).

5.2 EU policies to tackle gender and other gaps crossing research and innovation domains

In the latest decade, the European Union (EU) has actively championed gender equality in research through the implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in research organisations. These plans are considered instrumental tools for driving structural change given their potential to remove barriers to gender equality (GE), aligning knowledge production with an inclusive gender perspective throughout the entire research cycle.

The evolving landscape of research and innovation in the European Research Area (ERA) underscores the growing interconnection between scientific research and the economy. The [ERA Policy Agenda for 2022-2024](#), reaffirms gender equality as a priority for the current programming period, while through the [Ljubljana declaration](#), 37 parties including EU Member States, Associated Countries, Accession Countries and Third countries, have subscribed to key principles to fully acknowledge gender mainstreaming as a horizontal principle and jointly work on improvement in terms of gender equality, reaffirming the use of tools such as GEPs and emphasising the need for synergies within the ERA and beyond, “also within complementary fields such as the European Higher Education Area, cohesion policy funds, innovation ecosystems, as well as in international cooperation”.

As recalled, the [ERA Communication in 2020](#) sets gender equality in research and innovation as a priority, with the aim to increase the share of women in research careers, achieving gender balance in leadership positions, and integrating a gender dimension into research content and methods, as well as fostering inclusive gender inclusive cultures. This goal is increasingly seen as achievable only by addressing the entire research and innovation pipeline, emphasising the intersectoral mobility of researchers and tackling gender gaps throughout the process. European policies are paying increasing attention to linkages between research and innovation realms. The ERA Policy Agenda reaffirms the target of investing 3% of GDP in research and development (R&D) by European Member States (currently averaging 2.19%) as a critical investment for economic growth, especially in the post-COVID-19 recovery period. Promoting various forms of interaction and exchange between the research sector, the economy, and society, including citizen engagement and citizen science, is actively encouraged.

Recent discussions have centred on expanding ERA's gender equality objectives to the private sector and improving the alignment between research policies and innovation. For example, [GENDERACTION Policy Briefs](#) have proposed actions that highlight the need for commitments and clear goals in the wider private sector involved in research commercialisation and as potential employers of STEM (female) researchers. Indeed, the ERA is also becoming more interconnected with the European Education Area (EEA) to promote synergies between education, research, and service to society. These changes are the result of policy developments spanning the last two decades and are expected to expand further in the next EU programming period.

These EU-level policy developments gain further momentum as the European Commission has committed to linking access to Horizon Europe funds with the mandatory adoption of GEPs in public research institutions, by establishing [GEPs with specific requirements as pre-requisites to access Horizon Europe](#) funding for all public bodies. Given the growing synergies between Horizon Europe, European Regional Development Funds, and Erasmus+, these changes are expected to have a far-reaching impact, potentially extending beyond universities and public research organisations.

The CALIPER Charter promotes an intersectoral approach to inclusive gender equality in R&I ecosystems, being aligned with ERA policies and the Horizon Europe GEP requirement. It calls for even greater and more in-depth mainstreaming of an inclusive gender approach in both research and innovation.

5.3 In progress list of signatories

1. Lina Donnarumma, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Italy, on an individual basis
2. Andreea Diaconescu, National Institute for Chemical Pharmaceutical Research and Development Romania, HR generalist on behalf of my organization
3. Angela Stela Ivan, Dunarea de Jos" University from Galati Romania, Romania, on behalf of my organization
4. Camelia Serban, Ministerul Transporturilor, Romania, on behalf of my organization
5. Beatrix Ferenczi, University of Medicine and Pharmacy "IULIU HAȚIEGANU" Cluj-Napoca Romania, Romania, on behalf of my organization
6. Amalia STEFANIU, National Institute of Chemical Pharmaceutical Research & Development – ICCF, Romania, on behalf of my organization
7. Guldan Kalem, Yasar University, Turkey, on an individual basis
8. Magdalena Velciu, Ana Aslan International Foundation Romania, on behalf of my organization
9. Sara Aguirre, Université libre de Bruxelles, Belgium, on an individual basis
10. Oana Dima, National Organisation for Fiscal Administration, Romania, on an individual basis
11. Alessandra Del Monte, Obiettivo Famiglia Federcasalinge per la Liguria, Italia, on an individual basis
12. Andreea Bereczki, Romanian Diversity Chamber of Commerce, Romania, on behalf of my organization
13. Mariana Carmen Chifiriuc, University of Bucharest, Romania, on behalf of my organization
14. Monica Stroe, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Romania, on an individual basis
15. Anamari Nakic, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing University of Zagreb, Croatia, on behalf of my organization
16. Marcella Corsi, MinervaLab, Sapienza Università di Roma, Italy, on an individual basis
17. Brigita Miloš, Centar za ženske studije pri Filozofskom fakultetu u Rijeci, Croatia, on an individual basis
18. Ioanna Staneglouidi, Finclude Ireland, on behalf of my organization
19. Panagiota Rouni, National Technical University of Athens, Mechanical Engineering School, Greece, on an individual basis
20. Efthimia Tritopoulou, Greek Women's Engineering Association, Greece, on behalf of my organization
21. Riva Lava, National Technical University Athens, Greece, on an individual basis
22. Stella Kasdagli, Women On Top, Greece, on behalf of my organization
23. Magy Kontou, SimpleApps, Greece, on behalf of my organization
24. Ioanna Spyropoulou, National Technical University of Athens - School of Rural, Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, Greece, on an individual basis
25. Andreas Raptopoulos, WELLICS LTD, UK, on behalf of my organization
26. Gianna Tsakou, MAGGIOLI spa, Italy/Greece, on behalf of my organization
27. Vedrana Miholic, CROZ Croatia Business/Industry, Croatia, on behalf of my organization
28. Michel Verstraeten, Université libre de Bruxelles, Belgium, on behalf of my organization
29. Ulpiana Kocollari, UNIMORE, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy, on behalf of my organization
30. Silvia Fierascu, West University of Timisoara, Romania, on an individual basis
31. Antigone Kyrousi, The American College of Greece, Associate Professor, on an individual basis
32. Selin Atış, Yasar University, Turkey, on behalf of my organization

33. George Pantazis, National Technical University of Athens - School of Rural, Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, Greece, on an individual basis
34. İrem Özgören Kınılı, Izmir Katip Celebi University, Turkey, on an individual basis
35. Pol Kolokoussis, National Technical University of Athens - School of Rural, Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, Greece, on an individual basis
36. Burkay Pasin, Yaşar Üniversitesi, Turkey , on an individual basis
37. Konstantinos Athanasopoulos, National Technical University of Athens - School of Rural, Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, Greece, on an individual basis
38. Andriani Skopeliti, Technical University of Athens - School of Rural, Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, Greece, on an individual basis
39. Harris Vangelis, National Technical University of Athens - School of Rural, Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, Greece, on an individual basis
40. Nikos Tzelepis, National Technical University of Athens - School of Rural, Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, Greece, on behalf of my organization
41. Maria Papadopoulou, National Technical University of Athens - School of Rural, Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, Greece, on an individual basis
42. Maria Bezerianou, National Technical University of Athens - School of Rural, Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, Greece, on an individual basis
43. Rocío Segura-Nebot, UOC, Spain, on an individual basis
44. Anastasios Doulamis, National Technical University of Athens, Greece, on an individual basis
45. Pina Milišić, IEEE Croatia Affinity group Women in Engineering, Croatia, on behalf of my organization
46. Dia Anagnostou, Hellenic Foundation for European & Foreign Policy (ELIAMEP), Greece, on an individual basis
47. Rusudan Jobava, Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia, Georgia, on behalf of my organization
48. Tamar Tsertsvadze, Tbilisi State University, Georgia, on an individual basis
49. Manon Kodua, Georgian Technical University, Georgia, on an individual basis
50. Anabella Di Tullio, GenTIC-IN3-UOC, Spain, on an individual basis
51. Tamar Tskhadadze, Ilia State University, Georgia, on an individual basis
52. Coline Leclercq, UNamur, Belgium, on an individual basis
53. Barbare Nozadze, Ivane Beritashvili Center Of Experimental Biomedicine, Georgia, on an individual basis
54. Francois-Xavier Fievez, Université de Namur, Belgium, on behalf of my organization
55. Eri Pavlaki, Women Do Business, Greece, on behalf of my organization
56. Gvantsa Chigogidze, Georgian Technical University, Georgia, on behalf of my organization
57. Miruna Bivol, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC) - IN3, Spain, on an individual basis
58. Nikola Dmitrović, XV. gimnazija, Zagreb, Croatia, on behalf of my organization
59. Maria Sangiuliano, Smart Venice srl, Italy, on behalf of my organization
60. Marzia Cescon, Smart Venice srl, Italy, on an individual basis
61. Elene Rusetskaia, Women's Information Center, Georgia, on behalf of my organization
62. Teimuraz Dochviri, Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia, Georgia, on behalf of my organization
63. Indra Weber, Université libre de Bruxelles, Belgium, on an individual basis
64. Eleni Karachaliou, Aristotle University Of Thessaloniki, Greece, on an individual basis
65. Dimitra Hadjipavlou-Litina, Aristotle University Of Thessaloniki, Greece, on an individual basis
66. Maria Michali, Aristotle University Of Thessaloniki, Greece, on an individual basis

67. Kyriaki Karydou, ViLabs OE, Greece, on an individual basis
68. Vasiliki Moumtzi, ViLabs OE, Greece, on behalf of my organization
69. Ioanna Chouvarda, AUTH, Greece, on an individual basis
70. Gloria Bonder, UNESCO Chair on Women, Science and Technology in Latin America, Argentina, on behalf of my organization
71. Ketevan Jakeli, LEPL Zurab Zhvania School of Public Administration, Georgia, on behalf of my organization
72. Francesca Spagnoli, EnoLL, Belgium, on an individual basis
73. Nicola Marsden, Hilbronn University, Germany, on an individual basis
74. Anna-Maria Sansoni, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy, on an individual basis
75. Miriam Sefcikova, AUDIT-CONSULT Ltd, Slovakia, on an individual basis
76. Milos Cambal, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia, on an individual basis

